

SEARCH FOR NEW ANTISPASMODICS. PART III

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Synthesis of α -acetamid- β -liethylamino-propiophenone and of the corresponding β -piperidino analogue is described.

Recent survey of antispasmodics shows that the effective ones are generally salts of strong tertiary bases and even the heterocyclic compounds like isoquinoline, when particularly substituted at the 3-position with a methyl group (cf. Kreitmair, *Arch. Exp. Path. Pharm.*, 1932, **164**, 509; B. P., 488,423; Sugaswa and Sugimito, *J. Pharm. Soc. Japan*, 1941, **61**, 62; Polgar and Zelenka, *Magyar Nogyoaszok Lapja*, 1948, **7**, 1), are being found to exhibit pronounced antispasmodic activity. These observations have now stimulated the synthesis of compounds of the type (1), which may be regarded as cleavage products of 1:3-dimethylisoquinoline derivatives in which the hydrogen of the 3-methyl group has been substituted by a tertiary basic group. In this connection it should be mentioned that some secondary and tertiary amines, which bear relationship to the structure obtained by the hypothetical cleavage of the isoquinoline ring in completely hydrogenated papaverine, have proved to be potent antispasmodics (Blicke and Monroe, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, **61**, 91).

As the methylene group in ω -acetylaminoacetophenone is reactive, the latter has now been subjected to the Mannich reaction to yield, when condensed with formaldehyde and a secondary amine, the propiophenone derivative (1, R = diethylamino or piperidino). The base (1) generally separates as a pasty solid, but readily yields crystalline hydrochloride. The corresponding picrate and methiodide have also been prepared.

(1)

Bruson and MacMullen (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, **63**, 270) have shown that the bases, obtained by the Mannich reaction with phenols, split off, when treated with acetic anhydride, the tertiary amino groups, the latter being replaced by acetoxy groups. In a similar manner, 2-dimethylaminomethyl-3-pyridol has yielded, on treatment with acetic anhydride, 2-acetoxymethyl-3-acetoxypyridine, with the elimination of the dimethylamino group (Stempel and Buzzi, *ibid.*, 1949, **71**, 2969). However, the base, obtained by the Mannich reaction of 2-methyl-3-pyridol with diethylamine, has been found to be quite stable towards acetic anhydride, so far as the splitting off of the tertiary amino group is concerned (Stempel and Buzzi, *loc. cit.*). When the compound (1,

R=diethylamino) is heated at 135°-140° for 3 hours with excess of acetic anhydride, besides a small quantity of a non-basic compound, the major portion of the compound has been recovered unchanged. The non-basic compound, however, was of pasty nature and could not be purified and characterised.

The preliminary observations (A. N. Bose, *private communication*), as made on the isolated guineapig ileal and jejunal pieces of small intestine by measuring the relaxation which the drug in question produced against the normal tone of the intestinal musculature, tend to show that the hydrochlorides of both the compounds (I, R=diethylamino and piperidino) possess antispasmodic activity. Full details of the spasmolytic activity will be published elsewhere in due course.

EXPERIMENTAL

o-Acetamido- β -diethylamino-propiofenone (I, R=diethylamino).—A solution of *o*-acetylamino-acetophenone (17.7g., 0.1 mole), paraformaldehyde (3g., 0.1 mole) and diethylamine (9.1 g., 0.125 mole) in absolute alcohol (125 c.c.) was heated under reflux on the water-bath for 1 hour, when a further quantity of paraformaldehyde (3 g.) was added. The solution was further heated for 3 hours and the alcohol was then distilled under reduced pressure. The residue was treated with ice-cooled hydrochloric acid (2.5%) and filtered. The clear filtrate, on basification with ammonium hydroxide under cooling, yielded a pasty solid (15.5 g.) which is very soluble in alcohol, acetone and ethyl acetate, and sparingly soluble in ether. The pasty mass, however, could not be induced to crystallise under customary conditions.

The *hydrochloride* was obtained as a brownish crystalline powder by adding dry benzene, saturated with dry hydrochloric acid gas, into a dry benzene solution of the above substance, till just acid to Congo red. It was recrystallised from absolute alcohol-benzene mixture as a crystalline powder, melting at 160-61° with frothing and decomposition. (Found: N, 9.12. $C_{15}H_{22}O_2N_2$, HCl requires N, 9.38 per cent).

The *picrate* was obtained as yellow needles, melting at 140-41° to a dark, viscous liquid. (Found: N, 14.47. $C_{15}H_{22}O_2N_2$, $C_6H_3O_7N_3$ requires N, 14.25 per cent).

The *methiodide* was obtained by heating under reflux for ten minutes a solution of the compound in dry benzene with excess of methyl iodide. The precipitated solid was crystallised from absolute alcohol-ether mixture in brownish rectangular plates, which swelled up on heating above 100° with gradual evolution of gas and melted at 204° to a red, viscous liquid. (Found: I, 30.88. $C_{16}H_{25}O_2N_2I$ requires I, 31.44 per cent).

o-Acetamido- β -piperidino-propiofenone (I, R = piperidino).—The method of preparation was the same as in the case of the previous compound (I, R = diethylamino). Using a mixture of *o*-acetylamino-acetophenone (17.7 g.), paraformaldehyde (6 g., in two instalments) and piperidine (10.6 g.) in absolute alcohol (125 c.c.), the yield of the product was 16.2 g.

The above condensation was also effected by using equivalent quantity of piperidine hydrochloride instead of the free base. The residue, left after removal of alcohol under reduced pressure, was treated with cold water and filtered. The clear aqueous solution, on basification with ammonium hydroxide, furnished the product in an almost

the same yield. In both cases a pasty solid was obtained, which is very soluble in most of the organic solvents and sparingly soluble in ether. It could not be induced to crystallise.

The *hydrochloride* was similarly prepared as in the previous case and was recrystallised from absolute alcohol-benzene mixture as a brownish crystalline powder, melting at $170-71^{\circ}$ with frothing and decomposition. (Found: N, 8.68. $C_{14}H_{22}O_2N_2$, HCl requires N, 9.01 per cent).

The *picrate* was obtained as yellow needles, melting at 143° to a dark viscous liquid. (Found: N, 13.85. $C_{16}H_{23}O_3N_2$, $C_6H_3O_7N_3$ requires N, 13.92 per cent).

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